

CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF MARKET INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT IN AGRICULTURAL SECTORS.

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Abstract

In this article, the conceptual basis of market infrastructure development in agricultural sectors, the project of rural infrastructure development, its strategies and principles, the main tasks and directions of agricultural development until 2030, "Agricultural and food sector The main principles of the project to support the inclusive transition to the "green economy" and the development of the climate-oriented agricultural knowledge and innovation system, the strategy and implementation of the 2020-2030 strategy and implementation of the agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, analytical information about the ways to improve the management of the infrastructure of regional agricultural sectors of agriculture is highlighted.

Key words

Agricultural infrastructure, modernization, diversification, infrastructure, investment attractiveness, green economy, "Roadmap", innovative system, agrocomplex enterprises, agribusiness environment.

The Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan plans to implement the "Development of Rural Infrastructure" project in 2020-2024.¹¹⁴

More than 300 villages of Andijan, Fergana, Namangan, Jizzakh and Syrdarya regions of Uzbekistan will participate in the project and will have the opportunity to receive funds to improve the quality of basic social infrastructure in these settlements. The project was implemented with the financial support of the World Bank and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB). The World Bank provided a loan of 100 million US dollars and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank provided a loan of 82 million US dollars. The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has allocated 1.6 million US dollars for this purpose, and the total cost of the project is 183.6 million US dollars.

¹¹⁴ https://yumh.uz/en/news_detail/387

The project is aimed at improving the quality of the basic infrastructure of the rural population and improving the quality of services that provide the vital activities of the village covered by the project. Also, the project will help the local self-government system to improve the local self-government system by involving the villagers in assessing the basic needs of the infrastructure services provided in their neighborhood and in the decision-making process for further development.

The project is based on five main principles:

The following are defined as the main tasks and directions of agricultural development until 2030:

❖ which envisages the development and implementation of the food safety state policy to ensure the safety of food products and improve the consumption ration, to ensure the agricultural industries with the required amount and purchasing power of food products ensuring food security of the population;

❖ envisages further liberalization of trade, development of quality control infrastructure, reduction of trade transaction costs and promotion of exports, increasing the competitiveness of agribusiness at the expense of agricultural sectors with high added value agricultural and food products that can compete in the target international markets creating an enabling agribusiness environment and value added chains;

❖ reduction of state participation and increase of investment attractiveness in the field, which involves increasing the flow of private investment capital to modernize, diversify and support sustainable growth of the agriculture and food industry;

- ❖ rational use of land and water resources, forest management, and natural resources that provide for environmental protection and ensuring environmental protection;
- ❖ development of modern systems of public administration, which involves the restructuring and further development of the public administration structure in order to ensure the transition from administrative administration to market economy;
- ❖ it is intended to increase the effectiveness of state spending on agricultural support through the gradual distribution of budget funds in accordance with the new priority directions of state policy aimed at increasing labor productivity, improving product quality, and increasing high added value. Diversification of public spending aimed at supporting the catchment industry;
- ❖ the system of agricultural science, education, information and consulting services, which envisages the creation of an effective system of agricultural knowledge and information dissemination, integrating research, education and consulting services with agricultural sectors development;
- ❖ development of rural areas, which involves supporting the balanced and sustainable development of rural areas;
- ❖ development of a transparent system of network statistics, which involves the development and implementation of effective systems of statistical data collection and data collection, analysis and dissemination.¹¹⁵

table 1

"Supporting the inclusive transition of the agriculture and food sector to the "green economy" and developing a climate-oriented agricultural knowledge and innovation system. (UAKIS)" project.¹¹⁶

No	Indicators	Project content
1	Project status	In practice
2	The duration of the project	From September 2021 to September 2025
3	Project budget	4,150,000.00 Euros
4	SDG	Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation Goal 13: Action to combat climate change Goal 15: Conserve terrestrial ecosystems

¹¹⁵ <https://kun.uz/uz/54944102>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.undp.org/uz/uzbekistan/projects/qishloq-xojaligi-va-oziq-ovqat-sektorining-yashil-iqtisodiyotga-inklyuziv-otishini-qollab-quvvatlash-va-iqlimga-yonaltilgan>

5	Type of activity	Development of knowledge and innovation system in the field of agriculture
6	Project partner	Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan
7	The purpose of the project	<p>Facilitate an inclusive transition to a green economy in the agricultural and food sector of Uzbekistan and introduce a climate-friendly system of knowledge and innovation in agriculture in Uzbekistan.</p> <p>Specific goals include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In line with the Government of Uzbekistan's broader commitments under the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC), National Adaptation Plan (NAP) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), policies to promote green investments across the agri-food value chain and support the progressive development and implementation of knowledge-based regulations. 2. Establishment of "Agriculture and Food Sector Innovation Brokerage Services" (integrated into UAKIS) to mobilize local knowledge and capacity, expand climate-based investments to meet present and future needs of farmers and agribusiness, public and private to attract financing and scale up climate-based investments to meet the current and future needs of farmers and agribusinesses, as well as support climate-resilient livelihoods for rural people. 3. Innovative "farm-level" projects, primarily small-scale, to test and demonstrate green methods for climate change adaptation and agricultural practices and, where appropriate, transformative recovery from the impacts of COVID-19 and practical implementation covering smallholder farms, farmer cooperatives and micro-enterprises of the agro-industrial chain.
8	Expected results	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1: Creation of innovation and intermediation support services in agriculture and food sector. This result is achieved by implementing the following activities: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. Support the improvement of the policy and regulatory framework to support innovation in the agriculture and food sector to effectively establish intermediary services and to scale up the same against climate change in this sector. - support and assistance. 1.2. Institutional capacity building and cooperation among members participating in the UAKIS system to support innovation in the agriculture and food sector and provide effective services through intermediary services. 1.3. Joint planning and selection of project portfolios 1.4. Creation of continuous feedback, training and knowledge management system within UAKIS. 2: Create operational teams and partnerships to support innovation in agriculture and food:

		<p>2.1. Establish agri-food innovation operational groups and bring other new innovation proposals for transitioning to climate-friendly agriculture and green agri-food value chains.</p> <p>2.2. Organize training, capacity building and technical consulting for members and partners of innovation operations teams.</p> <p>2.3. Provision of targeted financial support and investments for innovative projects on the introduction of technologies for adapting to climate change and mitigating its consequences.</p> <p>2.4. Establish networking and information exchange programs to promote innovation in other regions/provinces.</p>
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The "Roadmap" for the implementation of the strategy and implementation of the agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 was approved.¹¹⁷

The priority directions of the strategy were defined, among them:

- development and implementation of the national food safety policy;
- wide implementation of market principles in the purchase and sale of agricultural products, development of quality control infrastructure, promotion of exports, creation of a favorable agribusiness environment and value-added chain, implying high value-added agriculture and food agricultural sectors;
- introduction of mechanisms to reduce state participation in the sector and increase investment attractiveness;
- rational use of natural resources and improvement of the environmental protection system;
- development of modern management systems, which implies restructuring and further development of the structure of state administration in agriculture;
- increasing the efficiency of state expenditures and gradual redistribution by developing network programs aimed at increasing labor productivity in farms, improving product quality, and creating high added value;
- development of the system of science, education, information and consulting services, etc.

Important tasks and measures for the rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates, including the establishment of large wholesale and trade centers, logistics, modern shopping centers in each region,

¹¹⁷

https://www.norma.uz/oz/qonunchilikda_yangi/qishloq_hujaligida_bozor_mehanizmlari_rivojlantiriladi_va_ilmiy_uslublar_joriy_etiladi

mobile sales points in rural areas trade centers are being established in the border areas to increase and allow the population to carry out free trade.

Also, in order to ensure consistency in this regard, it is decided to develop a program of measures for the development of trade services and road infrastructure every year in the regions. It is planned to establish 30 market and trade complexes, 13 large and 1000 small roadside infrastructure facilities this year. Today, the total value of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent is 6.1 trillion, total of 41 large shopping complexes and 364 billion soums in Andijan (1), Namangan (1) and Tashkent (3) regions. Construction of 5 logistics centers worth soums is underway.¹¹⁸

The strategic goal of the state policy in the field of infrastructure of agricultural sectors of agriculture is to form such a system that is guaranteed to meet the economic, legal and other requirements of agricultural sectors. It is not only a branch, but also of national and political importance, because the level of service to the agricultural sector largely determines the quality of life of the entire population. In this regard, it is necessary for the state to pay special attention to the infrastructure of the agricultural sector along with agriculture.

It is necessary to pay special attention to the interests of the agricultural sector, regulation of labor relations, relations of infrastructure sectors with suppliers of material and technical means and other economic resources. Regulation of the market infrastructure, as well as further improvement of the structures that manage it on a territorial scale, based on the introduction of modern information technologies. In order to ensure the normal functioning of the main and auxiliary agricultural sectors in the conditions of the market economy, communication processes based on modern technical means have a special place. It is necessary to create an effective system of infrastructural management of property and objects remaining in state ownership. In order to achieve the goal of effective operation of the infrastructure of agricultural agricultural sectors in the region, issues of improving the level of local management are being prioritized. A special place should be given to marketing services that are not currently used in management systems. This applies especially to the marketing of services of agricultural industries of service enterprises. At the same time, life promotes the need to increase the competitiveness of infrastructure objects of the agricultural sector in the state and local service markets.

¹¹⁸ <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/hududlarda-savdo-infratuzilmasi-rivojlanyaptimi>

Other directions for improving the management of the infrastructure of regional agricultural sectors of agriculture are also necessary.

In particular, the following is necessary for the conditions of our republic:

- to support the development of all forms of ownership and business management, the formation and operation of market infrastructures not only in agriculture, but also in the service sector;

- development of state programs for the development of the infrastructure of agricultural sectors of agriculture;

- to achieve quality information and consulting support for agrocomplex enterprises, organizations and institutions in general and in particular the infrastructure of agricultural sectors;

- to support the development of integration processes and cooperation both in agriculture and in the infrastructure of agricultural sectors;

- to be able to distinguish the functions of state and economic management;

- organization of centralized management of the complex of services of agricultural industries to agricultural enterprises.

Consideration of the problems of developing the infrastructure for production services, the logistics of the agro-industrial complex allows us to conclude that in modern conditions the forms of interaction, both consumers and suppliers, are significantly changing. The expansion of market relations, the growth in the number of separate economic entities involve new types of goods and paid services in the market. The market of resources and services in the regions has taken on a new shape. Material and technical resources and repair and technical services on the market are controlled by a limited number of manufacturers, trading companies, service structures, which creates the prerequisites for the creation of large corporate systems with an extensive network. This puts forward additional requirements, dictates the need for the development of globalization in agriculture. The creation of large integrated structures, both in the field of agricultural production and in the providing infrastructure sector, is the imperative of the times.¹¹⁹

REFERENCES:

1. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/pr-campaign-affect-marketing-function-38569.html>

¹¹⁹ <https://fundamental-research.ru/ru/article/view?id=30111>

2. <https://ogahiy.tsuos.uz/ozbekiston-iqtisodiyotini-yashillashtirish-istiqbollari/>
3. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yashil_iqtisodiyot
4. <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/yashil-iqtisodiyotga-otish-kontseptsiyada-qanday-maqсадlar-kozlangan>
5. <https://www.undp.org/uz/uzbekistan/press-releases/yashil-rivojlanish-qishloq-xojaligi-va-suvdan-foydalanish-ortasidagi-aloqa>
6. Abdullayeva H. QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA IXTISOSLASHGAN KLASSTERLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH HOLATI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 7. <https://marketer.ua/ru/swot-analysis-types-features-pros-and-cons/>
7. Саидова Ф. К. Современное состояние и направления развития аграрного сектора Республики Узбекистан //СОВРЕМЕННОЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРИРОДНОЙ СРЕДЫ И НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ПРИРОДОПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ. – 2016. – С. 3673-3675.
8. SAIDOVA F. ХУДУДЛАР ИҚТИСОДИЁТИДА САНОАТ ТАРМОҒИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИ СТАТИСТИК ТАҲЛИЛИ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2023. – Т. 30. – №. 30.
9. Khakimovna A. F. ANALYSIS OF THE ACTIVITIES OF AGROCLUSTERS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 5. – С. 153-157.
10. SAIDOVA F. KLASSTER DOIRASIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH KOOPERATSIYASINI TASHKIL ETISH VA YURITISHNING IQTISODIY KONSTITUTSIYASI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2023. – Т. 35. – №. 35.